

THE DEVELOPING STUDENTS' COMMUNICATION AND INTERACTION SKILLS

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The actuality of this article is determined for the modern education of our republic as enormous. Opportunities to learn English are provided in many different ways such as through formal instruction, travel and study abroad as well as through media and the Internet. In recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on the development of communicative skills among students in higher education institutions. Effective communication skills are essential for academic success professional advancement, and social interaction in today's globalized, and interconnected world. Recognizing the importance of communicative competence, many higher education institutions have implemented various programs and interventions aimed at enhancing students' communication skills. Learning should be staged so that the learner builds the multiple skills required in expert performance and discovers the conditions under which they apply. Apprentices are inducted into a community of expert practice in which the "teacher" continuously engages in and is a master at the practice being learned. Teacher's performance constitutes the standard for the apprentice. Teachers are wise to point their students directly toward clear learning goals - to tell students exactly what knowledge they will be gaining and how they can use that knowledge.

Key words: apprenticeship, span, vocational, domain, content, method, feedback, hint, reminder, scaffold, apprentice, promote, assessment, provide, participate, referee, monitor, assumption, destination, skill, experience.

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For the past 25 years' connections have been becoming inevitable among nations, organizations and countries which create a huge need for knowing another language. People need to use international languages in areas, such as trade, tourism international, relations between governments, technology, science and media. First of all, language, which is a means of communication, can be practiced in a natural environment, whether, in the family, in the community or in an organized manner. Knowledge of languages is especially important in today's world of international relations. The range of technologies are available for use in language learning and teaching has become very diverse. Control over learning in the hands of the teacher undercuts the student's development of cognitive management skills, including goal - setting strategic planning, monitoring evaluating and revising capabilities critical for effective learning. Students develop no confidence in their own ability to learn or in their own sense - making abilities and their opportunities to learn from experience are highly constrained.

There are many various methodology and instructional approaches to achieve their objectives. Many programs adopt experiential learning approaches, that provide students with opportunities to engage in real - world communication tasks and activities. This may

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include role-playing exercises, group discussions, case studies. Simulations, and collaborative projects that stimulate authentic communication contexts and challenges. Active learning often incorporates active learning strategies that encourage students' participation. This may involve interactive lectures, reflective exercises and hands-on activities that promote active engagement with course content and deeper understanding and retention. Another consequence of passive learning is that since students are not drawn into the learning process, they adopt a "waiting - it - out" attitude, investing minimal attention and involvement in the learning process.

Another source for ideal about effective learning is how individuals learn in traditional apprenticeships. Whereas school curricula tend to be a specification of practice, apprenticeships arrange opportunities for practice. Jordan (1987) identified several characteristics of traditional apprenticeship learning including. Work is the driving force. The progressive mastering of tasks by apprentices is appreciated not as a step towards a distant, symbolic goal (such as a certificate), but for its immediate value in getting the work done.

Apprentices start with skills that are relatively easy and where mistakes are least costly. Teachers and teaching are largely invisible. In apprenticeship learning and in formal job training in American workplaces -it looks as though little teaching is going on. Whatever instruction the apprentice receives, originates not from a teacher teaching but from a worker doing his or her work that the apprentice observes.

In short, apprentices are inducted into a community of expert practice in which the "teacher" continuously engages in and is a master at the practice being learned. His or her performance constitutes the standard for the apprentice.

Clearly, traditional apprenticeships are not entirely transferable to a modern society where many skills, such as mathematics, law computer – based machining, are at best only partly visible. Because of this, cognitive scientists have conducted a number of trials of effective learning situations and curricula appropriate for learning today's less visible practices. These efforts span a number of subjects – mathematics, physics, reading, writing and interior design.

These precedents – nineteenth century innovations, analyses of traditional apprenticeships and of the spectacular learning by a young child, actual attempts by cognitive scientists to create different kinds of learning environments and an extensive body of cognitive science research add up to a solid foundation for designing effective learning environments. Collins, Brown and Newman (1989) have proposed a model of "cognitive".

Incorporating key elements of those environments.

The model ignores the usual distinctions between academic and vocational education, its objective being to initiate the novice into a community of expert practice. The model presumes that learning is learning, however we label the subject. In fact, as the American economy and its skill requirements restructure, many "vocational" domains involve substantial amounts of symbolic activity and the distinction between vocational and academic is rapidly becoming less useful.

The Collins, Brown and Newman model has four building blocks - "content", "methods", "sequence" and "sociology". Many parts of this model are not new, but together they define an effective learning situation, with very different classrooms and roles for teachers and students.

Schools usually focus exclusively on the concepts facts and procedures of a subject. To operate effectively in any setting, however, students also need three other types of content:

1. “Tricks of the trade” – problem – solving strategies that experts pick up with experience.
2. Cognitive management strategies – goal setting, strategic planning, monitoring, evaluation and revision.
3. Learning strategies – knowing how to learn, including exploring new fields, getting more knowledge in a familiar subject and reconfiguring knowledge already possessed.

Teaching methods should give students the chance to observe, engage in, Invent or discover expert strategies in context. The Collins, Brown and Newman model includes a variety of methods that systematically encourage student exploration and independence. Teachers’ coach – offering hints, feedbacks and reminders; provide “scaffolding” – support for students, as they learn to carry out tasks and “fade” – gradually handing over control of the learning process to the student.

Learning should be staged so that the learner builds the multiple skills required in expert performance and discovers the conditions under which they apply. This requires a sequence of increasingly complex tasks, increasingly diverse problem – solving situations, and the staging of learning so that students develop a feel for the overall terrain before attending to details.

The learning environment should reproduce the technological, social, time and motivational characteristics of real-world situations where what is being learned will be used. It is only through encountering subject matter knowledge applies for the situations. For example, in the real-world people have to work with others; this model calls for students to work together to solve problems and carry out tasks.

According to the cognitive research covered in how people learn environments that best promote learning have four interdependent aspects – they focus on learners, well – organized knowledge, ongoing assessment for understanding and community support and challenge.

Teachers must realize that new knowledge is built on existing knowledge.

Teachers need to uncover the incomplete understandings, false beliefs and naive renditions of concepts that students have when they begin a course.

If these are ignored, students may develop understandings very different from what the teacher intends them to gain. Knowledge – centered environments take seriously the need to help students learn the well – organized bodies of knowledge that support understanding and adaptive expertise. Teachers are wise to point their students directly toward clear learning goals – to tell students exactly what knowledge they will be gaining and how they can use that knowledge. In addition, a strong foundational structure of basic concepts will give students a solid base on which to build further learning.

Assessment – centered environments provide frequent formal and informal opportunities for feedback focused on understanding, not memorization, to encourage and reward meaningful learning. Feedback is fundamental to learning, but feedback opportunities are often too scarce in classrooms. Students may receive grades on tests and essays, but these are summative assessments that occur at the end of projects. What are needed are formative assessments that provide students with opportunities to revise and improve the quality of their thinking and understanding. Community – centered environments foster norms for people learning from one another and continually attempting to improve. In such community students are encouraged to be active, constructive participants. They are encouraged make – and learn from mistakes.

The most effective learning environments contain all four of these Interdependent aspects. So, teacher need to keep these his mind all the time.

Teachers should demonstrate fairness and respect by providing all students with access to learning and by encouraging them to feel that they and their ideas are valued in the classroom. Feeling respected will help students feel safe enough to take risks and use their creativity in classroom activities.

Teachers in communicative classrooms will find themselves talking less and listening more – becoming active facilitators of their students' learning.

The teacher sets up the exercise, but because the students' performance in the goal, the teacher must step back and observe, sometimes acting as referee activity or monitor. A classroom during a communicative is far from quiet, however. The students do most of the speaking and frequently the scene of a classroom during a communicative exercise is active, with students leaving their seats to complete a task.

Because of the increased responsibility to participate, students may find they gain confidence in using the target language in general. Students are most responsible managers of their own learning. In a typical audio-lingual lesson, the following procedures would be observed: 1. Students first hear a model dialogue (either read by the teacher or on tape) containing key structures that are the focus of the lesson. They repeat each line of the dialogue individually and in chorus. The teacher pays attention to pronunciation, intonation and fluency. Correction of mistakes of pronunciation or grammar is direct and immediate. The dialogue is memorized gradually, line by line. The line may be broken down into phrases, if necessary.

2. The dialogue is adapted to the students' interest or situation, through changing certain key words or phrases. This is acted out by the students.

3. Certain key structures from the dialogue are selected and used as the basis for the pattern drills of different kinds. Some grammatical explanations may be offered at this point, but this is kept to an absolute minimum.

Nowadays most of the English language learners are becoming increasingly interested in the concept of content creation – the process of gathering information relevant to a particular topic or area of interest and sharing it with peers. Technology also affords learners the opportunity to record themselves and present them to peers.

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